

A route for synthesis of 1,3,5-trisubstituted naphthalenes by reaction of *ortho*-substituted benzylisoquinilium bromides with α,β -unsaturated ketones

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Abstract : Three *ortho*-substituted cycloimmonium bromides : *ortho*-chlorobenzylisoquinolium bromide, *ortho*-bromobenzylisoquinolium bromide and *ortho*-nitrobenzylisoquinolium bromide have been prepared by the reaction of *ortho*-substituted benzyl bromide with isoquinoline in benzene in an atmosphere of nitrogen at reflux temperature in good yields. These isoquinolinium salts on reaction with base generated corresponding *ortho*-substituted benzylideneisoquinolium ylides *in situ*. The reaction of these salts or ylides with a wide range of substituted benzylideneacetophenones in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ or ZnCl₂ in mixture of ammonium acetate and acetic acid gave 1,3,5-triarylnaphthalenes in good yields. Aluminium chloride or zinc chloride in acetic acid is used as cyclisation agent. The structures of naphthalenes were confirmed by elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectral data.

Keywords : Yildes, isoquinolinium ylides, isoquinolinium salts, dizonium salts, naphthalene.

Introduction

Literature survey reveals that pyridinium, α -picolinium phosphonium and arsonium ylides have gained considerable importance in the synthesis of acyclic, cyclic and heterocyclic compounds¹⁻⁸. Thus our attention was directed towards utilization of isoquinolinium ylides for the synthesis of naphthalene derivatives. A convenient route in this regard was first reported by Krohnke's *et al.*⁴ for the synthesis of diarylnaphthalene derivatives which involved the condensation of benzylpyridinium bromide with benzalacetophenone in presence of ZnCl₂ in acetic acid. It was a convenient method⁴ for synthesis of naphthalenes because it involved single step and gave better yield of products. Tewari and Gupta *et al.*⁸⁻¹⁰ also extended the reaction of pyridinium ylides and reported the detailed experimental conditions for the preparation of 1,3-diarylnaphthalenes. We were prompted and encouraged by these reports to investigate an alternative route for the synthesis of naphthalene derivatives which involved the reaction of isoquinolinium salts and ylides with α,β -unsaturated ketones. Herein, we reveal the results of our study leading to the synthesis of trisubstituted naphthalenes.

Results and discussion

The reaction of *ortho*-substituted benzyl bromide with isoquinoline in benzene at reflux temperature under nitrogen atmosphere gave *ortho*-substituted benzylisoquinolinium bromides (**1a-c**). The structures of these isoquinolinium salts (**1a-c**) were determined on the basis of IR and NMR data^{11,12}. The NMR spectrum of salts **1a-c** showed a singlet at δ 6.35 typical of methylene protons and aromatic protons appeared in the range δ 6.85-8.35. The reactions of these salts **1a-c** were carried out with a wide range of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds in presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ or ZnCl₂ in presence of mixture of sodium acetate and acetic acid at 200 °C to give 1,3-diaryl-5-substituted naphthalenes (**5a-7m**) in 50-75% yields. It was, however, observed that the yields of the naphthalenes were dependent upon the nature of substituents attached to isoquinolinium salts (**1a-c**) as well as on α,β -unsaturated ketones. The reactivity of salt **1c** was lower than salts **1a-b** because of electron withdrawing nature of NO₂ group which stabilized carbanion formation. Hence, **1c** afforded lower yields of naphthalene derivatives than the salts **1a-b**.

The course of reaction seems to proceed via the intermediacy of betaine type derivatives **4** which is formed by

a nucleophilic attack of the ylide carbanion **2a-c** generated *in situ* by dehydrohalogenation of salts **1a-c**, on β -carbon of α,β -unsaturated ketones **3**. Betaine **4** then undergoes cyclisation in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl_2 or AlCl_3 used as cyclization agent to afford naphthalenes **5a-7m** (Scheme 1). The course of reaction is similar to pyridinium ylides⁸⁻¹⁰.

Scheme 1

All the naphthalenes gave satisfactory elemental analysis. The IR spectral data of naphthalenes showed a double absorption maxima in the region 1630–1620 cm^{-1} which were assigned to the stretching vibrations of carbon-carbon double bond. The strong bands in the region 910–850 cm^{-1} were diagnostic absorption of polynuclear aromatics. The nitro groups of the products showed a strong symmetrical stretching band in the range 1355–1335 cm^{-1} . The NMR spectral data of compounds in general exhibited aromatic multiplets in the range of δ 6.55–8.60, methyl protons at δ 2.25–2.30 and methoxy protons at δ 3.75–3.80.

Experimental

All the reagents obtained from commercial sources (E. Merck, BDH, Fluka and SISCO). Melting points were recorded on Gallen Kamp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer using KBr phase. Varian A-60 and Varian A-100 spectrometer were used to record NMR spectra using TMS as an internal standard.

Preparation of *ortho*-substituted benzylisoquinolinium bromides (**1a-c**) :

A solution of isoquinolinium (50 mmol) and *ortho*-substituted benzyl bromide (50 mmol) in 50 ml of anhydrous benzene was allowed to reflux on water bath for 4–

Table 1. Physical properties of naphthalene derivatives (**5a-7m**)

Compd. ^a	X	Ar ₁	Ar ₂	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. ⁶ M.p. (°C)
5a	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	60	92–94	94–96
b	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	109–111	108–110
c	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	64	124–126	125–127
d	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	56	108–110	110–112
e	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	3,4-O ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₃	65	134–136	133–135
f	Cl	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	67	120–121	121–122
g	Cl	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	62	96–98	95–97
h	Cl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	55	192–193	190–191
i	Cl	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅	60	170–172	170–172
j	Cl	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	62	173–174	171–174
k	Cl	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	67	189–191	190–192
l	Cl	4-C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	65	162–164	160–162
m	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	72	173–174	172–173
6a	Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	68	92–93	94–96
b	Br	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	113–115	112–114

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

c	Br	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	75	124-126	126-128
d	Br	C ₆ H ₅	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	72	115-116	114-116
e	Br	C ₆ H ₅	3,4-O ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₃	74	131-133	132-134
f	Br	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	78	118-120	120-122
g	Br	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	64	98-100	96-98
h	Br	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	62	190-192	189-191
i	Br	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅	59	172-174	174-176
j	Br	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	70	175-177	176-178
k	Br	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	62	192-194	191-193
l	Br	4-C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	60	161-163	162-164
m	Br	2-C ₄ H ₃ S	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	64	172-174	174-176
7a	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	45	91-93	94
b	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	48	110-112	112
c	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	42	132-134	128-130
d	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	50	111-113	115
e	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	3,4-O ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₃	45	132-134	133
f	NO ₂	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	35	120-122	118-120
g	NO ₂	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	45	94-96	96
h	NO ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	48	190-191	188
i	NO ₂	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅	38	173	171-172
j	NO ₂	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	52	176-177	178
k	NO ₂	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	32	189-191	192-194
l	NO ₂	4-C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	47	164-166	165
m	NO ₂	2-C ₄ H ₃ S	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	50	176-178	177

^aCompounds gave satisfactory analytical data.

6 h. A solid mass precipitated which was filtered, dried and recrystallized twice from chloroform : *n*-hexane (1 : 2) to give isoquinolinium salts as detailed below.

o-Chlorobenzylisoquinolinium bromide (**1a**) in 80% yield, m.p. 210-212 °C; IR (KBr); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3050 (C-H attached to =N⁺-CH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ , ppm) : 6.30 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.70-8.40 (11H, m, ArH).

o-Bromobenzylisoquinolinium bromide (**1b**) in 75% yield, m.p. 142-144 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3055 (C-H attached to =N⁺-CH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ , ppm) : 6.30 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.65-8.45 (11H, m, ArH).

o-Nitrobenzylisoquinolinium bromide (**1c**) in 90% yield, m.p. 158-160 °C; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3050 (C-H attached to =N⁺-CH₂), 1515 and 1300 (NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ , ppm) : 6.40 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.78-8.40 (11H, m, ArH).

Preparation of 1,3-diaryl-5-substituted naphthalenes (5a-7m) : General procedure :

A mixture of isoquinolinium salts **1a-c** (30 mmol) and α,β -unsaturated ketones (**3**) (30 mmol) was stirred at 200 °C in presence of anhyd. ZnCl₂ (3.0 g) or AlCl₃ (3.0 g) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and ammonium acetate (3.0 g) for 6-9 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture, after keeping overnight at room temperature, was poured into ice cold water (20-30 ml) when a solid mass precipitated. The solid mass so obtained was separated by filtration, washed with water and dried. The product was subjected to column chromatography over neutral alumina and benzene as eluent. The product was recrystallised from suitable solvent to give good yields of the titled compounds (Table 1).

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